

Research Article

Overview of Corruption and Anti-Corruption in Bangladesh

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Abstract This study aimed to provide basic information on overview of corruption and anti-corruption legislation in Bangladesh. It indicates the impact of corruption on the economy, sector-wise corruption and how poor enforcement of existing laws has led to corruption. The proposed study analysis of the theoretical and conceptual interpretations of “corruption” and “corruption interaction”, discussion of the reasons and conditions for the development of bribery interaction in these countries, as well as consideration of the official assessments of anti-corruption activity and the main directions of prevention and combating corruption from society. Within the structure of this article, we analyze mostly current official positions, investigative materials, hypothetical and theoretic forms and research perspectives, in which current structures and practices of bribery interaction in these countries are being problematized. This study also looks into the implementation of various reform initiatives including development of an impartial and fair system, establishment of code of ethics, reform in political parties, election process, legislations and government policies are crucial with anti-corruption measurements.

Keywords: Bribery; Anti-Corruption; Legislative Framework; Anti-Corruption Commission; Policy; Public Procurement; Enforcement Agency

Introduction

Corruption in Bangladesh is widespread and permeates all levels of society; the rule of law is weak and the most institutions lack transparency and integrity structures. This is reflected in the country’s poor performance in most areas assessed by governance indicators. Political parties, public administration, the judiciary and the police are perceived as the most corrupt institutions of the country [1]. Bangladesh has made significant improvements in the fight against corruption in the last decade. However, patronage networks influence Bangladeshi public life and the

malfunctioning of democratic institutions, dominated by the opaque ruling parties undermine the country's efforts to reduce corruption and poverty [2]. The People's Republic of Bangladesh was established as a constitutional, democratic, unsanctified, legislative republic and multiparty. After independence in 1971, Bangladesh went through periods of poverty and deprivation, as well as political confusion and military coups. The restitution of democracy in 1991 was followed by considerable advances in economic, social and political evolution [3]. However, the current environment in the densely populated and overcrowded country continues to remain vaporous as it undergoes substantial economic and social change (UNDP 2019). Bangladesh has crucial very much clarified regulatory foundation all over the country, in spite of the fact that it is unacceptable in certain regards (Bertelsmann Stiftung 2019) [4].

Although, Bangladesh has made exceptional progress on economic performance that has helped to decrease poverty and social disproportion. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth of Bangladesh was assessed to have reached at 7.9% in 2019 and its forecast to tumble to 2% in 2020 because of the outbreak of the COVID-19 and get to 9.5% in 2021, as per the updated International Monetary Fund (IMF) estimates from 14th April 2020 [5]. Regardless of these victories, the nation despite everything faces some scary difficulties with around 22 million people whom are as yet living beneath the poverty line, and corruption being extensive in various sectors (World Bank 2019; Bertelsmann Stiftung 2019), Corruption, extortion, fake cash, medicate dealing, gold pirating and dealing in people are the fundamental wellsprings of ill-conceived continues [6].

The main objective of this study is to understand the factors contributing to bad performance of the anti-corruption agency and legislation framework in the context of governance structure in Bangladesh. This research also highlights the gap between the policy decision of ACC and legislation framework to promote people's desire and reality of policy implementation that faded people's aspiration.

Methodology

This study discusses the various corruption in public sector in Bangladesh at an institutional level through a study of its highlights and current status. It subsequently analyzes and assesses the efficacy of corruption anticipation measures and the public perception of these measures. We did not conduct any primary survey. We collected data from secondary sources i. e. journal, reports, news reports. After receiving all some articles, we sorted out the valuable materials which are

directly related to our topic. After sorting out, we studied the selected articles. All the information of one article is not necessary. That is why we picked up the information which directly matches with our research. Most of the study materials collected from the internet. In some cases, we studied some history books to see the difference before the present decade.

Discussion and Findings

Recent preventive measures in Bangladesh is effective in decreasing corruption opportunities, but not in enhancing the public trust of the government. These countries have the own anti-corruption law with agencies [7]. Although most of the Asian countries are applying their own laws and regulation and legal institutional framework, along with international convention to control corruption is well developed and the country receives high scores in terms of anti-corruption law and institutions [8]. Based on 2019 Corruption Perception Index reported by Transparency Bangladesh scored 26 points out of 100 (see Figure 1).

The scholars believe that the word "good governance" will bring about the diversity of public administration because the World Bank (WB) used the term in 1989 for the first time to solve government administration problems. In developing countries but didn't get the awareness as because it was a negative vocabulary. The meaning of "good administration is" good at accepting the trust of the legislature in providing great assistance or service and eminence and being a portion of sorting out meetings, reacting, regarding and being ethical and comprehensive, and consenting to the guidelines of law.

In addition, the degree of the political framework must be conducive for accepting the most assistance cash since it is the most significant in light of the fact that it decides the long-term progress. Adjusting deviations utilizing great administration with the capacity and approval and making a social framework that can be found in all sectors of society through nonstop congruity with three reforms [9]. The government must reform the structure of the identity of the procedure work of the legislature is a system for managing social assets to be transparent, legit, productive and effective in carrying public services to you. The fame and working techniques for government representatives will be valuable to crafted by the administration. It is essential to reform and encourage the business sector to have a policy that can be checked and verified [10]. Have service standards and can work fully with the state and the non-government sector or public divisions,

political, economic, social and political principles and national liabilities, that can be a positive result to control the corruption.

Analytic Outcomes

Figure 1. According to the Corruption Perceptions Index announced by Transparency International the corruption index of Bangladesh is 26 points out of 100 in 2019

Overview of Corruption in Bangladesh

Bangladesh has gone up against a large group of political difficulties since its independence in 1971. After the compensation of majority rules system during the 1990s, the reins of intensity have wavered between Sheik Hasina and Khaleda Zia. The nation is beset with endemic corruption. While laws to address corruption exist, they are not executed enough, nor are significant foundations useful [11].

1.1 Extent of Corruption

Bangladesh ranks 146 out of 180 nations in Transparency International's 2019 Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) with a score of 28/100 (Transparency International 2019) with 0 designating the most elevated impression of corruption and 100 the least. Bangladesh additionally ranks inadequately in various administration related issues including corruption, based on the

Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) by the World Bank (2019). Bangladeshi citizens additionally perceive corruption as a significant issue in their nation, practically 50% of the respondents observe that corruption has expanded in Bangladesh in the previous 2 years and including the individuals who imagine that the degree of corruption remained the equivalent carries the number to 64%. Moreover, 72% of the reviewed residents detailed having encountered corruption in the most recent year [12].

1.2 Political and Grand Corruption

Corruption is so predominant at both small- and large-scale levels that it intimidates to turn into a method for living. Elites in Bangladesh may well have operated the political procedure to suit their own advantages, similarly as they have created multifaceted corrupt practices both to tend their companions and to save their own positions in power. This offers increment to the wonder of what Mungiu-Pippidi calls "particularism", a method of social association described by the foundational dispersion of public merchandise on a non-universalistic premise that reflects the brutal circulation of intensity inside such social orders. Not many anti-corruption crusades set out to jump the radicles of corruption in social orders where particularism is the standard, as these radicles lie in the dissemination of intensity itself. Corruption is to be found at all levels in practically all sectors of government, just as scarcely any private organizations [13].

The resource of party financing is one of the greyest regions where unaccounted cash is kept. There is no particular review or administrative system set up to research or investigate wellsprings of party financing (Bertelsmann Stiftung 2018). While a few cutoff points on gifts or contributions exist, parties and applicants or candidates are both dependent upon reductions on spending during efforts; proof proposes that limitations on both spending and contributions are penetrated normally.

1.3 Insignificant and Bureaucratic Corruption

However, salaries in the public sector have expanded in the course of the most recent couple of years, yet bribery still stays extensive and comprises a primary wellspring of salary of public authorities in Bangladesh. As per TI Bangladesh, the trudge in compensations has not assisted with preventing corruption because of the incentive structure that permits public authorities to remove bribes as public office holders are seldom exposed to judicial or parliamentary investigation. Corruption in public office is extremely high just as in organizations uniquely experience

corruption while assessing public administrations [13]. About portion of organizations envision giving assistance installments to public authorities "to complete things". Nepotism, trickery, corruption and sporadic installments during the time spent granting government contracts are perceived as incredibly normal.

There is a high danger of corruption in the Bangladesh land organization. Organizations pass on deficient trust in the administration's capability to ensure property rights. Bangladesh's first famous development embarrassment is the breakdown of an eight-story garment factory in April 2013, which slaughtered or killed more than 1,100 individuals. The industrial facility experienced a faulty development that penetrated construction regulations [14]. The occurrence features the gigantic issue of an absence of good administration, constrained assets, adulterates associated with authorizing and allows, or conspiracy between plant proprietors and wellbeing assessors, which permits offices to stay operational despite the fact that risks are distinguished, a lot to the burden of laborers' wellbeing and security (Business Anti-Corruption Portal 2018).

1.4 Public Administration Corruption

Analysts discern that bribery, rent-seeking and improper utilization of government funds, intemperate importuning, extended delays in service performance, purloining, irresponsible demeanor from government officials, and imprudent bureaucratic intemperance and ethos have made public sector departments related with law implementation, education, water supply, gas supply, electricity, health, waste disposal, transportation, issue of passports and maintenance of land records susceptible to bribery. Lack of proper accountability emerges to have also been a cause for this susceptibility to bribery. The World Economic Forum's Global Competitiveness Index 2017–2018 ranks Bangladesh 99/137 based on the following parameters:

- Diversion of public assets – 75/137;
- Nepotism in decisions of government authorities – 106/137;
- Strength of scrutinizing and reporting standards – 120/137.

Politicization of enrollment in universities and schools influence the standard of education in Bangladesh [13]. The healthcare sector is also widespread with cases of grand and trivial corruption. Healthcare candidates up-and-comers are known to offer incentives to get better administrations, access to ambulances and some of the time to help the administrations. Private

healthcare institutions recruit unregistered specialists or doctors and specialists with imitation capabilities or regularly neglect to utilize the legally required least number of specialists and care staff.

1.5 Judiciary

Although on paper the judiciary is independent and has been segregated from the executive since 2007, the executive still maintains control over judicial consultations, and the judiciary remains intently aligned with the executive branch. Anti-corruption attempts have been enfeebled by politicized enforcement and subversion of the judicial process under the obligatory AL government [15]. The judiciary executive doesn't generally protect the fair right to a reasonable and public preliminary or trial because of corruption, bias, and delicate HR and institutional limits (US Department of State 2019). Organizations face a high danger of corruption in the Bangladesh judiciary framework. Corruption is seen to be extensive in lower courts. Judges, lawyers and other court authorities frequently request or demand bribes from respondents or rule dependent on steadfastness to generosity systems.

1.6 Security Forces

The police force is the foremost bribe institution, followed by the civil service, political parties and the courts in Bangladesh. There is an unreasonable risk of corruption when interrelating with Bangladesh police. Businesses ranked the Bangladesh police as one of the tiniest dependable or reliable in the world and eminent business expenses due to crime and violence (Business Anti-Corruption Portal 2018). Law implementation or enforcement organizations were also found to be the public frameworks with whom citizens are most anticipated to experience bribery according to the National Household Survey 2017 conducted by Transparency International Bangladesh (TI-B) (TIB 2018).

Security forces reportedly availed commination, battering, kneecappings and electric shocks even some officers also committed rape and other sexual abuses or harassments all with indemnity (US Department of State 2019). The auditor general of Bangladesh, the parliament and the anti-corruption watchdog are repeatedly unenthusiastic to inspect the military and are even actively averted from doing so [15]. The military also controls or operates the Trust Bank and the Ansar VDP Bank and has a record of proffering illegitimate loans from these institutions to top officers.

Based on the BBC investigation, the Bangladesh Army’s business profits further comprise power plants, roads, infrastructure and bridge projects, amounting to billions of dollars of private assets.

1.7 Bribery Circle in Project Enforcement of Union Parishad

Anti-Corruption Reforms in Bangladesh

Bangladesh has taken notable steps forward in the brawl against corruption, through institutional reforms, succession to the UNCAC and the assumption of new codification. Despite the top levels of bribery in the country, Bangladesh citizens perceive their government as productive or even very effectual in the brawl against corruption. However, there are various gaps and delicacies in Bangladesh’s anti-corruption institutional framework. One of the most significant gaps in Bangladesh’s rectitude system is the absence of an inspector. The Bangladesh Constitution accommodates a provision inspiring the initiation of an Office of the inspector or Ombudsman the consecutive governments have neglected to implement it. Furthermore, political thoughts or deliberations systematically effect the anti-corruption agenda. The existing codification or legislation and organizations are frequently utilized to plague political rivals and current developments [16].

2.1 Strategies of Anti-Corruption

Bangladesh is a democratic and developing country emerged as an independent country in 1971 through a gory war. The vision was to make a prosperous Bangladesh. But the aspiration diminishes away within few years for ubiquitous corruption and violation in running the state equipment. In 2004 the government of Bangladesh proceed Anticorruption Act to avert corruption and other corrupt enactments or legislation in the country and to performance inquiry and inspect for other particular crimes. The Commission incorporates of three commissioners and a chairman between them. According to law the commission has privilege to void its obligation [17]. The commission is in charge of inquire, scrutinize, file and conduct cases concerning to bribery offences. It is also invested to recognize or identify the sources of corruption, execute research on anticipation of corruption, exhibit symposium, factory etc. In respect of any investigate or inspection into assertion of corruption the commission has the following potentials:

- Writ witness, certify or ensure their aspect and interrogate them under oath;
- Discover and present document;
- Take proofs or evidences under oath;
- Call for public records or its certified copies from any court of office;
- Issue warrants for the interrogation of witness and the investigation of document;
- Any other incident needed for perceiving and attaining the aims and purposes of this law.

2.2 Strategies of Government to Curb Corruption

- Restructure the Anticorruption Commission and Making it effectual;
- Evolution of National Taskforce on Anticorruption;
- Citizen's authorization;
- Government proffer rule to government employee to submit the declaration of their annual assets and prosperity to concerned department;
- Evolution of Truth and Accountability Commission;
- Realization or awareness building;
- Restructure several important state frameworks including Bangladesh Public Service Commission, Bangladesh Election Commission;
- Dissociation of Judiciary from administrative branch of government.

2.3 International Conventions

Bangladesh signed and certified the United Nation Convention against Corruption in 2007 (UNCAC 2018). The country also ratified the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime in 2011 (UNTC 2018).

2.4 Domestic Legitimate Framework

Bangladesh will celebrate 50 years of autonomy or independence in 2021. In this situation, there are different imminent projects like Vision 2021, the seventh Five Year Plan (7FYP) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and the nation has organized countering bribery in all these strategic operations. For example, in Vision 2021, a political platform from the Awami League contends the inclination of government to brawl against corruption for sustainable progress, and goal 5 (of 8) is to rid society of corruption. The Code of Criminal Procedure, the Anticipation or prevention of Corruption Act, the Penal Code and the Money Laundering Prevention Act criminalize attempted bribery, exaction, active and passive corruption, corruption of foreign public officials, and utilizing public assets or confidential state information for individual advantage (Business Anti-Corruption Portal 2018). The Anti-Corruption Commission Act dispense the legitimate framework for the independent anti-corruption commission (ACC) to secure transparency in the public sector (Business Anti-Corruption Portal 2018) [18].

2.5 Institutional Framework

A National Integrity Strategy (NIS) was endorsed by Cabinet in October 2012. Afterwards, NIS sections have been initiated at every service and a National Integrity Advisory Committee has been set up with the Prime Minister as its Chair [19]. The overall aim or objective of a National Integrity Strategy is to yield a system of governance that generates belief among citizens. The Government also schemes to initiate an Ethics Committee composed of the heads of the organizations.

2.6 Anti-Corruption Commission

In Bangladesh, the (ACC) was founded in 2004 as a neutral and independent organization under the Anti-Corruption Commission Act of 2004; and it addresses anti-corruption in three broad categories: legitimate or licit, organization or institutional and other actors. In 2016, the government forced the Anti-Corruption Commission (Amendment) Bill through parliament, which

re-legitimized police to trace cases of deception, falsification and avoiding under eight sections of the penal code [16]. A sense of indemnity is common as the ACA has never inmate any high-profile politicians or business elites. Based on the ACC's 2015 annual report, poor conviction rates due to poor-quality or inferior investigations led to the exoneration of 207 out of 306 people convicted of corruption. Most defilement or corruption cases are politically impacted, and public trust in the ACC is absent.

2.7 Office of the Comptroller and Auditor General

The Office of the Comptroller and Auditor General (OCAG) is as the nation's incomparable review organization and is responsible for evaluating government receipts and public committing. It is likewise in control with finding whether consumptions have surrendered an incentive for cash in government offices, public systems and legislation organizations. Assigned by the president of the republic, the comptroller and auditor general (CAG) [20], and chiefs of the supreme audit institution. CAG has the ratification to regulate the scope and range of auditing.

2.8 Law Enforcement

A remarkable effort has been made to enhance rectitude in the country's law enforcement organization is the Police Reform Program (PRP), sponsored by international development partners. It is an inclusive capability building initiative aimed to provide more effectual and representative police force (UNDP 2015) [21]. Despite this, law implementation frameworks still engross the highest rank in civilians 'experience of corruption according to TIB's 2018 National Household Survey (TIB 2018).

2.9 Media

The Bangladesh Constitution concedes the "the right of every citizen to freedom of speech and assertion, and freedom of the press." The Bertelsmann Foundation certifies the Bangladeshi media to be miscellaneous and vigorous, albeit so often being affiliated to political parties. The Right to Information Act subscribes to give journalists better access to government data and information, particularly in relation with investigative reporting. The media and investigative journalism play a vital role in conducting proclamation of corruption to light and acting against indemnity. Media reporting is an indispensable albeit untapped source of perception or detection in corruption cases.

International consortiums of investigative journalists are an example of an international collaboration that leads to substantial results in conducting economic and financial crime to the awareness of the public and law implementation authorities (OECD 2018) [22].

Based on the World Press Freedom Index by Reporters Without Borders Bangladesh ranks 150 among many other nations in the world in 2019. Freedom House (2019b) evaluates that the press in Bangladesh as “not free”, physical violence and menaces against journalists and bloggers continue with indemnity, murders endure unsolved and other acts of violence often go unpunished (Freedom House 2019b).

2.10 Civil Society

Civil society in any country plays a crucial role in anti-corruption assay. Not only does civil society act as a watchdog revealing incidences of corruption, it also extends awareness, suggests alternatives and provides a policy for an affiliation of actors to work together. Over the years, Bangladesh has become a vivacious nation for the relationship of a few organizations in its improvement example and jurisdiction structures, just as against corruption endeavors [23].

2.11 Transparency International Bangladesh (TIB)

Transparency International Bangladesh (TIB) is an independent, non-governmental, neutral and non-profit organization devoted to anti-corruption, good regime, accountability and transparency in the country (TIB 2018). It is a national section of the global anti-corruption NGO, Transparency International. The current 2014 to 2019 strategy, Building Integrity Blocks for Effective Change (BIBEC) focuses to reinforce a series of bilateral supportive and strengthen “integrity blocks” to effectively decline corruption. “Blocks” here implicit the pivotal organizations, policy/law, education, coaching or training, ethics and values, and above all, the people of the country (TIB 2018) [24] TIB’s website is fundamentally in English but has assets, reports and its bribery reporting tab in Bengali. It is highly informative on the bribery prospect and the organization’s activities; and is currently the only organization in Bangladesh entirely devoted to countering corruption.

2.12 The Centre for Policy Dialogue (CPD)

The (CPD) is an ivory-tower dedicated to donating towards participatory policymaking. It predominantly undertakes research and analysis, collocates dialogues, constructs publications and supports capacity building of relevant collaborator, CPD's research outputs and also its members have contributed to national and local policy changes and initiatives in assist of good governance, sound economic management and the interests of criticized groups in the society. The other CPD analysts have additionally contributed to the policymaking activity in Bangladesh as individuals from various department or councils and working groups such as the Bangladesh Bank, Organizing Commission, Ministry of Commerce, Ministry of Industries and Ministry of Agriculture. Its on-going research fields incorporate, however are not constrained to, organization, bribery, anti-corruption, and administration conveyance (CPD 2018) [25].

2.13 SHUJAN – Citizens for Good Governance

SHUJAN, which recognizes itself as an independent and non-partisan pressure group, was established in 2002 as a dynamism of a group of concerned citizens. Its object is the advancement of democracy, decentralization, electoral ameliorates, transparent politics and accountable administration (SHUJAN 2019) [23]. It assays to current the “voice of the people” to the government, policymakers and service-providing organizations (SHUJAN 2019).

2.14 BRAC

Building Resources Across Communities (BRAC), is an international non-governmental development institution based in Bangladesh enacted to social evolution or development in total of nine countries in Asia and Africa. It is also the comprehensive global antipoverty organization providing microloans, self-employment chances, health services, education, and licit human rights services. BRAC captivates in several social accountability dynamism at the regional level in all 64 districts in Bangladesh [24].

Conclusion

Based on this study on the overview corruption in these country and legal institutional framework employed by countries to combat corruption, it demonstrates that the overall corruption of these country is almost in the field of Political and imposing corruption, Insignificant and bureaucratic corruption, Judicial System, Legislation, Police, Security forces, Public Services, Land

Administration, Tax Administration, Custom Administration, Public Procurement, Natural Resources, and Civil Society. When discussing laws to combat corruption, we do not only concentrate on the criminal law and the laws of evidence, although they are undoubtedly important. The task of combating corruption is a continuous process but focusing on these elements alone ignores a wide array of necessary laws. These include legislation that covers, for example, criminal law, Anti-Money Laundering act, Anti-Terrorism Financing and Proceeds of Unlawful Activities Act, Anti-Corruption Act, Anti-Corruption Commission Act access to information, Right to information act, Customs Act, declaration of interest, public acquisition, freedom of articulation and the press, assurance of informants and complainants, blessings and cordiality, legal survey of the legitimacy of administrative actions, and others. We are not saying the government of Bangladesh is completely able to curb the corruption. When the country can't curb the corruption then change the policy and reform the law with increase penalties. There are various laws and institution in this country that contain anti-corruption assess. Not every one of them deal explicitly with corruption, but rather incorporate regulations that concomitantly focus at the anticipation of corrupt practices. An independent ACA is well known in numerous Asian countries, its adoption is effective with a favorable policy context.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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